
INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGLISH, LITERATURE, AND CULTURAL STUDIES

A MONTHLY, INDEXED, REFEREED AND PEER REVIEWED OPEN ACCESS INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

Volume 2. Issue 1. (April) 2025

CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF MARKETIZATION STRATEGIES OF SELECTED UNIVERSITIES OF EXCELLENCE IN GERMANY

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D.O.I: 10.5281/zenodo.15587187

Article Information

Received: 1st April, 2025

Accepted: 12th May, 2025

Published: 3rd June, 2025

Keywords: , Discourse Analysis;
Mercerization Strategies;
Germany

JOURNAL URL:

<https://ijois.com/index.php/ijoecls/index>

ABSTRACT

This paper analyzed the marketisation strategies deployed on the website of TUM in Germany using theoretical principle of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). The data were mined on 8th of April, 2023 from the official website of TUM, Germany. Rhetorical move analysis approach was adapted to unpack the marketization strategies in the “mission statement” on the website of TUM. The study concludes that dynamic linking of distinct discursive strands such as conversational, advertising and bureaucratic; built in and around the lexico-grammatical structure of “mission statement” on the website of TUM in Germany. The study further concludes that there is “glocalization” in the mission statement of TUM as one of the “universities of excellence” in Germany. In this interdiscursive analytical context, TUM is concurrently embracing the global market-driven values while still upholding a national instrumentalist ideology.

KEYWORDS: Discourse Analysis; Mercerization Strategies; Germany

PUBLISHER: Empirical Studies
and Communication–(A
Research Center)
Website: www.cescd.com.ng

Introduction

The role of university is to maintain their valued reputation and give back to society by dissipating non-utilitarian awareness, generate great scholars, and promote human growth (Alhojailan, 2020). The branding of university is a common trend today so as to show their uniqueness. Different branding techniques are used by different universities. The impact of branding otherwise known as marketization and promotional culture of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) discourse has been a key topic of concern among scholars. For instance, universities have been observed to use embedded commercial genres such as ‘entrepreneurial university’, ‘clients’,

'customers', 'educational entrepreneurship', 'markets', 'corporate identity', 'mission statement', among others (Connell & Galasinski, 1998; Mautner, 2005; Mayr, 2008; Xiong, 2012). Furthermore, the use of commercial embedded genres makes HEIs more appealing, interesting, and leading to increase in the enrolment levels of national and international students (Osman, 2008; Alhojailan, 2020). Therefore, incorporating Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) in the lexico-grammatical structure and marketization strategies of the "mission statement" of Technical University of Munich in Germany is indispensable.

Mission statement is defined as short statement that connotes the goals, existence and operations of an organization (Duke University, 2023). Mission statement is the pursuit of a goal that is unique to an organization's competitive advantage; its specific strengths and offerings relative to competitors while again emphasizing its values (Bowen, 2018). Mission statements are normally several sentences long with intension to answer the question of Why do we exist? This is because, Mission statements help management to organize the hierarchy of priorities that an organization must face in daily and long-term operations (Bowen, 2018). Although, some organizations prefer to post a brief mission statement, of only one to two sentences in length, so it can be more easily memorized and repeated while Other organizations use the mission statement as an opportunity to articulate critical information about their purposes and goals to investors and the general public (Duke University, 2023). Meanwhile, there are nine (9) detailed elements that mission statements often radiates such as customers; principal products/services; geographic / domain/market; technological advantage; economic goals/performance; philosophy; identity/ concern for public image; reputation/self-concept; and concern for employee (Bowen, 2018). In contrary, there is no specific number of elements in mission statement, rather, it should be informative, inspiring, enduring, concise, clear, and conducive to both employees and customers forming an emotional bond with the firm (Ghafoor, 2017). Hence, the mission statement of TUM which are critically discoursed in the later part of this paper is stated thus:

We inspire, promote and develop talents in all their diversity to become responsible, broad-minded individuals and empower them to shape the progress of innovation for people, nature and society with the highest scientific standards and technological expertise, with entrepreneurial courage and sensitivity to social and political issues, as well as a lifelong commitment to learning (TUM Website, 2023).

TUM was founded in 1868, and has been at the forefront of innovation. The university was founded to provide the state of Bavaria with a center of learning dedicated to the natural sciences. The university has played a vital role in Europe's technological advancement and has the prestige of having produced a number of Nobel Prize winners. Scientists today have the same goal as their 19th century counterparts: finding solutions to the major challenges facing society as we move forward. The new designation of "Technische Universitat Munchen was conferred in August, 1970. The introduction of the Bavarian Higher Education Law in 1974, the six faculties were replaced by eleven smaller departments; (i) Mathematics and informatics; (ii) Physics; (iii) Chemistry, Biology, and Geoscience (iv) Economics and Social Sciences (v) Structural Engineering and surveying; (vi) Architecture; (vii) Mechanical Engineering; (viii) Electrical Engineering and Information Technology; (ix) Agriculture and Horticulture; (x) Brewing, Food Technology and Dairy Science; (xi) Medicine.

Technical University of Munich in Germany is among the ten (10) universities that bears the hallmark of “University of Excellence” (Fintiba, 2023). The hallmark of Excellence Strategy was initiated in 2005 by the German government so as to develop university science and research (Fintiba, 2023). The universities selected for the hallmark are funded with millions of euros so as to invest in laboratories, cutting-edge technology that pave ways to scientists for outstanding international connections (Fintiba, 2023). Presently (2019-2026), ten (10) universities bears the hallmark of “excellence”. Out of the ten (10) ranked universities, Technical University Munich was ranked fifth (5). The rankings emanated from the World Universities’ ranking on Times Higher Education (THE). As at 2023, Times Higher Education ranked Technical University of Munich, Germany 30th on the global university ranking. Times Higher Education is a reliable global university ranking institution that provides unbiased and comprehensive global university rankings (Times Higher Education (THE), 2023).

Meanwhile, several studies have been carried on the discourse analysis lexicogrammatical structure of universities from developed and developing countries (Teo & Ren, 2019; Xiong, 2012), most of the studies are from China. However, there seems to be dearth of recent study on the discourse analysis of grammatical structure of marketization strategies of top ranked universities with “hallmark of excellence” in Germany, especially TUM. Likewise, there seems to be dearth of recent study that adopted Critical Discourse Analysis using genre methodology in the analysis of the marketization strategies deployed in the top ranked university with “hallmark of excellence” in Germany. There seems to be dearth of recent study that considered interdiscursivity of text and structure on the website of TUM. This is because, interdiscursivity connect the analysis of text with the analysis of the structures in the study phenomenon (Zotzmann & O’Regan, 2016). Hence, this study aims to analyse how Technical University of Munich in Germany advertise itself through its “mission statement” section by contributing to linguistic literatures.

The remaining aspect of this paper follow thus: literature review, methodology, discussion of findings, conclusion and areas of further studies.

B. Literature Review

This paper adopts theoretical principle of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), and complemented with two descriptive qualitative methodological approaches: first, genre analysis methodological approach as conceptualized by scholars (Swales, 1990; Bhatia, 2013). Second, the framework of Van Dijk’s Socio-cognitive Approach (Van & Teun, 2001; Ivana & Suprayogi, 2020). These principle and approaches have been used by previous studies (Teo & Ren, 2019; Ivana & Suprayogi, 2020). The use of CDA in the context of Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) have been numerous and varied (Teo & Ren, 2019). Based on the fact that CDA can represent how people use the language in the communication process (Afrianto, 2017). Also, CDA can analyze aspects of discourse, namely ideology, power, and hegemony (Ivana & Suprayogi, 2020). Hence, Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is an interdisciplinary approach to the study of discourse that views language as a form of social practice and focuses on ways of social and political dominance produced by texts and speeches (Priatmoko & Cahyono, 2013; Ivana & Suprayogi, 2020).

For instance, previous study (Teo, 2007) showed the discourse analysis of the

prospectuses of two university in Singapore which showed that government-subsidized public university adopted a more traditional university centered stance, while that of business oriented private university adopted a much less authoritative stance. The study further concluded that the form as well as the functions of the two universities in Singapore to certain extents, become business-like under the pressures of globalization and marketization (Teo, 2007). However, the study seems inadequate because Socio-cognitive approach seems to be the most appropriate methodology to be adopted because of its practicability. Furthermore, the selection of the two universities in this study is not scientific because justifications for selecting the two universities in Singapore for discourse analysis seems to be implicit. Further studies need to consider the identified areas.

Furthermore, previous study (Xiong, 2012) described the rhetorical moves and discourse strategies by elucidating an alternative way to understanding the marketization strategies deployed by higher education in China. The study considered 48 advertisements of university academic positions which reflects an intertextual mixing of bureaucratic and promotional discourses. Findings from the study are: first, the establishing-credentials move plays a vital role in promoting the relevant institutions; second, a striking rhetorical feature is the major use of computed terms to introduce items such as incentives; academic programs and facilities. Third, the branding strategy has been frequently adopted to publicize academic posts as well as cities where the institutions are situated; and fourth, some face redressing strategies are used to lessen the power asymmetry constructed by the authorless bureaucratic discourse. The study further shows a confluence between bureaucratic powers and market forces. The interplay of seemingly contradictory discursive strategies is construed based on negotiation between the universities' wish to maintain hierarchical authority and still embrace promotional culture (Xiong, 2012). Despite the robustness of findings of this study, there seems to be death of information showing the justification for the selection of the 48 universities used for this study; hence, validity and reliability attributes of this study seems not clear. Further studies need to consider the identified gap in this study.

Another study (Han, 2014) considered eighty-six (86) university presidents' speeches delivered at graduation ceremonies in China. The study revealed a predominance of authoritative discourse construed as reflective of the institutional reality indicate that, the operations of universities in China are controlled by the State. The study (Han, 2014) further revealed that the rhetorical strategies deployed in the presidents' speeches of the universities represent their efforts to adapting their uniqueness to socio-political context of universities in Chinese. The study concludes that marketization of higher education in China is complex and needs better understanding in its particular political, cultural and educational contexts. However, there are gray areas in this study that need clarifications, there is need to know the justifications for the selection of eighty-six (86) universities in China before analyzing their presidents' speeches. Furthermore, socio-cognitive approach seems to be appropriate for this study because of its intrinsic attributes. Further studies need to consider the identified gap.

Recent study (Teo & Ren, 2019) discoursed the global phenomenon of the marketization of top universities in China. The study analyzed the published presidents' messages on the websites of thirty-six (36) top-ranked universities in China, with the aim of ascertaining the extent to which the institutionalized genre imbricates marketization strategies with other essential ideologies. The study deployed

theoretical principles of CDA coupled with genre analysis methodological approach. Findings from the discourse analysis shows dynamic linking of three discursive strands; bureaucratic, advertising and conversational devised in and around the move structure of the presidents' messages. This interdiscursive analysis reveals competing imperatives and contestations that reflect the multiple roles of the presidents' messages to project a globalized, international outlook while maintaining an allegiance to political ideologies and national interests that top-ranked universities in China have to simultaneously negotiate.

This study (de Bernardi, 2019) presents an alternative perspective on the discussion on tourism marketing in relation to authenticity. The study analysed the websites of Sámi tourism companies from Sweden using CDA. The study implement retroduction in the context of analysis of the tourism's website by moving from what is empirically observable to the structures that are not immediately observable (Danermark, Ekstrom, Jakobsen, & Karlsson, 2002), such method usually involves patterns identification (de Bernardi, 2019). Furthermore, this study considered interdiscursivity by connecting the analysis of the text to the analysis of the structures on the website (Zotzmann & O'Regan, 2016; de Bernardi, 2019).

The discussion put forward in the study is not a generalizing picture of how the Sámi peoples in Sweden choose to market themselves, but it problematizes how these particular enterprises relate to issues of authenticity in the representation of cultural heritage. Findings from the study shows one side of a multifaceted discussion on the struggle between different discourses on representations and authenticity that are often the main channel to reach and attract potential visitors.

Another recent study (Alhojailan, 2020) examine how some Saudi universities advertise themselves. Incorporating Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), the study analyzes the "About Us" sections of seven Saudi universities' websites to explore the rhetorical moves and discursive strategies employed for marketization purposes. The selected universities all featured in the top 1000 universities in the QS World University Rankings 2020. The results show diversity in these universities' choices of implemented rhetorical moves and sub-moves. They used eight (8) rhetorical moves and thirteen (13) sub-moves, with only one (1) of these sub-moves occurring on all seven universities' websites. The discursive strategies were employed to foster self-promotion, while the results demonstrated that the "About Us" sections of all universities were promotional. Finally, some recommendations are provided for universities for marketization purposes if they want to be global and compete with other international universities in the higher education market, in addition to providing suggestions for future studies.

Another recent study (Ivana & Suprayogi, 2020) discusses a speech delivered by the United States President, Donald Trump, which discusses the conflict between Iran and America. The study was conducted to reveal the representation of Iran and the United States in one of Donald Trump's speeches. The method used in this study is the descriptive qualitative method. The data in the study are in the form of words, phrases, clauses, and sentences that indicate the position of Iran and the United States taken from the speech transcript from the official website of The White House. Data were analyzed under the framework of Van Dijk's Socio-Cognitive Approach, consisting of text, socio-cognitive, and social context. Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that Iran is described as a country that has nuclear ambitions and acts of terror that

support the existence of terrorists. On the other hand, America is described as having an invincible power. At a socio-cognitive level, Donald Trump is considered a knowledgeable figure on his country's political condition because he knows the weaknesses of Iran and can properly take every decision. The study shows that Donald Trump also has the authority as a President to make The United States and the countries of the world work together for peace. Thus, from the level of social context, countries in the world support the actions taken by America and are very alarming about what Iran has done. The finding suggests that the Socio-cognitive approach is practical to analyze the representation of an issue in speech, reflected in linguistics expression and the discourse structure. The study conclude that the representation of Iran and the United States can be seen from the structured feasibility through text analysis, social cognitive level, and social context level. At the text level, America is described as a country that has power and is invincible. While Iran itself is more represented in sentences detailing actions related to terrorism and nuclear. At a socio-cognitive level, Donald Trump appears to have extensive knowledge, which is demonstrated by his readiness to oppose attacks by Iran. Finally, the level of social context, in which countries declare that they support what America is doing, and regrettably acts carried out by Iran because if war will occur, it will affect peace and other aspects of the world. The analytical approach deployed in this study seems not broader, future interested scholars in conducting a broader analysis of representations of Iran and the United States can focus on relations with other issues, so that the accuracy and knowledge of the two countries will be broader (Ivana & Suprayogi, 2020).

C. Methodology

(i) Data

The data for this study were mined from the official website of Technical University of Munich (TUM), Germany. The data was obtained on 8th of April, 2023. TUM was selected for this study because of two reasons: first, Technical University of Munich in Germany is among the ten (10) universities that bears the hallmark of "University of Excellence" (Fintiba, 2023). Second, in 2023, Technical University of Munich, Germany was ranked 30th in global university ranking by Times Higher Education (THE); a reliable source known for providing unbiased and comprehensive global university rankings (Times Higher Education (THE), 2023). Furthermore, the two criterial were considered as benchmark for the selection of TUM based on their attributes: first, The hallmark of "Excellence Strategy" was initiated in 2005 by the German government so as to develop university science and research (Fintiba, 2023). The universities selected for the hallmark are funded with millions of euros so as to invest in laboratories, cutting-edge technology that pave ways to scientists for outstanding international connections (Fintiba, 2023). Second, Times Higher Education claims to be the only global university performance system to judge over 1250 research-intensive universities across areas like teaching, research, knowledge transfer and international outlook (Teo & Ren, 2019; Times Higher Education (THE), 2023). The university rankings globally escalate intranational and international competitive pressure among universities (Marginson & Van der Wende , 2007; Teo & Ren, 2019).

Furthermore, this study considered the English version of "mission statement" on the website of TUM in Germany. The fact that the website of TUM had an English version of "mission statement" implies a yearning to project an international, globalized image in line with marketization. Hence, the use of English Language as the lingua franca for dissemination of knowledge and academic communication is a result of the

internationalization and globalization of higher education (Teo & Ren, 2019). However, the use of TUM for this discourse might be predisposed to marketization, it would be interesting to examine the extent, and how, this marketization is broadly manifested in the “mission statement” on the website of TUM in Germany.

It is important to know that university websites are sometimes quite comprehensive and to analyse the entirety would exceed the scope of this study (de Bernardi, 2019), hence, the need to focus on the mission statement on the website of TUM. The chosen webpage for CDA seems to be the potential landing page for potential visitors or students when visiting the website to see programmes and activities offered in TUM.

(ii) Data Analysis

To unpack the marketization strategies in the “mission statement” on the website of TUM. A rhetorical move analysis approach developed from genre theory as conceptualized by scholars (Swales, 1990; Bhatia, 2013) and adopted by previous study (Teo & Ren, 2019) was used for this study. Following (Teo & Ren, 2019), a corpus-based rhetorical move analysis was conducted. First, a preliminary list of move types and their rhetorical functions were identified with reference to previous studies (Xiong, 2012; Teo & Ren, 2019). Furthermore, a tentative coding scheme was developed and used to pilot code a representative sample of “mission statement” on the website of TUM to test its robustness. The coding scheme extracted for pilot study was further revised in relation to the data, the coding schemes were reworked and upgraded. Based on this pilot coding, a new coding scheme comprising distinct attributes surfaced. An inter coder reliability check was to be done to establish coding reliability and validity using Cohen’s Kappa coefficient so as to determine the level of inter-coder agreement (Hartmann, 1977); further studies may consider checking inter-coder agreement of the six attributes.

The rhetorical move analysis to uncover the macro-structure of “mission statement” on the website of TUM, the micro-level lexico-grammatical features within the structure of “mission statement” on the website of TUM were examined to uncover the discursive strategies employed to achieve the rhetorical effects of “mission statement” on the website of TUM. Analytic concepts from systemic functional linguistics (SFL) (Halliday, 1994) were used to explore the identity construction, interpersonal meaning and organizational structures in “mission statement” on the website of TUM to uncover their ideological postures. Furthermore, SFL was used as focusing device for interpreting and explaining the rhetorical moves identified in “mission statement” on the website of TUM and not simply to describe the linguistic features of “mission statement” on the website of TUM. Furthermore, interdiscursivity was considered by connecting the analysis of the text to the analysis of the structures on the website (Zotzmann & O’Regan, 2016; de Bernardi, 2019).

On the basis of these macro- and micro-level analyses of “mission statement” on the website of TUM, various discourses that are embedded and covered the interdiscursive structure of “mission statement” as a whole were identified. It is believed that the analysis adopted for this study would offer insights into the extent and how the marketization strategy of TUM in Germany is discursively manifested.

D. Discussion of Findings

In the context of this analysis, mission statement on the web page of TUM was analysed to understanding how Technical University of Munich in Germany advertise

itself through its “mission statement” section by contributing to linguistic literatures. The mission statement of TUM is stated thus:

“We inspire, promote and develop talents in all their diversity to become responsible, broad-minded individuals and empower them to shape the progress of innovation for people, nature and society with the highest scientific standards and technological expertise, with entrepreneurial courage and sensitivity to social and political issues, as well as a lifelong commitment to learning (TUM Website, 2023).”

The marketization genres in the mission statement of TUM as entrenched in the guiding principles of TUM are stated thus:

“(i) innovation for people, nature and society; (ii) highest international standards; (iii) global mindedness and tolerance; (iv) talent with ethical substance; (v) value creation through diversity and appreciation; (vi) learning without borders; (vii) continuing education; (viii) entrepreneurial thinking and action; (ix) cross-generational approach; and (x) dialogue with society and the public (TUM Website, 2023)”.

The macro rhetorical structure of the mission statement shows the rhetorical moves based on the lexico-grammatical features analysis of the mission statement of TUM as entrenched by its guiding principles. Furthermore, ten (10) interweaving discursive strands that constitute the interdiscursive structure of the mission statement of TUM were realized. Hence, three discourses identified in the mission statement to highlight the particular ways in which the marketization of TUM in Germany is discursively manifested. The discourses strands are: Bureaucratic discourse; conversational discourse; and advertising discourse. These strands of discourse are explained thus:

(i) Bureaucratic discourse

TUM is one of the prestigious universities in Germany bearing the hallmark of excellency. As the time of gathering the data used for this study, the university has benefited and still benefiting humongous grants, funding and supports from Government of Germany. This reflects in their operation according to “a quasi-bureaucratic system modeled on the government (Xiong, 2012; Teo & Ren, 2019). The hallmark of “excellency university” that TUM is official recognized with it its affiliation is discursively reflected in the mission statement of TUM in Germany. For instance, the bureaucratic connections of TUM as “underlined, italics and bold” by phrase that allude directly to its governmental affiliation and support as stated thus:

(a) ... sensitivity to social and political issues...

Based on the given example above, TUM allude their affiliation with the Germany Government. More than simply an act of obeisance, this can also be seen as a strategy to bolster the university’s status and attractiveness in the eyes of the prospective student, both local and foreign, likewise the foreign government. For instance, with the highest scientific standards and technological expertise...

(ii) Conversational discourse

As much as hallmark “excellence university” in Germany pledge allegiance to their government whose support and endorsement then serve to uplift and strengthen their status in Germany’s HEIs, they are susceptible to the global forces that are transforming education into a business in the international market. Universities around the world are no longer function merely as an ivory tower of knowledge and scholarship but to varying degrees, profit-oriented corporations competing for

government funding and student revenue as they chase after league table rankings such as THE and QS. Excellence universities” in Germany are not exception.

The need to further promote university in Germany as ‘world-class’ institution that can compete with other global universities and attract the best and the brightest has re-shaped the discourse of Germany’s higher education in distinct ways. One way is by adopting a conversational style to effect a friendly, intimate and interactive posture. As a genre, conversation not only indexes informality but also assumes an egalitarian relationship between the interlocutors (Teo & Ren, 2019). The conversational discourse is manifested in the opening lines of the mission statement of TUM:

(b) ... We inspire, promote and develop talents in all their diversity to become responsible, broad-minded individuals and empower them to shape the progress of innovation for people, nature and society, Based on the emphasis above, it is observed that the mission statement was opened with personal pronoun “we”. This personal pronoun used creates a colloquial, informal tenor and thus simulates a close relationship between the mission statement of TUM and readers. Furthermore, the use of personal pronoun “we” can be seen as an attempt to imitate the customer-oriented discourses of the market to draw readers to the university and can be seen as an instantiation of advertising discourse commonly used in the tourist industry (Askehave, 2007; Teo & Ren, 2019).

(iii) Advertising discourse

Advertising discourse features are inherent in the mission statement of TUM apart from the use of conversational features to creating a friendly interpersonal stance. The advertising discourse features are in numerous forms such as: the foregrounding of particular qualities believed desirable to prospective students, alumni members and other stakeholders. Among the salient advertising discourses of TUM is stated thus:

- (c) “We inspire, promote and develop talents in all their diversity to become responsible, broad-minded individuals and empower them to shape the progress of innovation for people, nature and society
- (d) ...with the highest scientific standards and technological expertise...
- (e)with entrepreneurial courage
- (f)as well as a lifelong commitment to learning

The four stated distinct attributes of advertising discourse in the mission statement of TUM center on is having to incubate and accelerate the idea of students to start up. Meaning that, students with business idea would have built a sustainable business by the time they are graduating (see example c). Furthermore, the advertising discourse in example c shows that by the time their students would be graduating from their school, they would have become green innovators or green-preneurs. More so, the second advertising discourse (in example d) shows the element of excellency in the university. Hence, ...highest scientific standards and technological expertise... is touted by the mission statement of TUM. Another distinct attribute of advertising discourse used in the mission statement of TUMwith entrepreneurial courage... shows that they dedicated to the principle of competitive achievement. Furthermore, their basic and applied research to market-oriented innovation processes and promote an “entrepreneurial spirit” in all areas of the university.

Lastly, the distinct attribute that many of the university foreground is having a rich heritage and long history. This foregrounding is syntactically realized through a process of positioning adverbial elements encoding the university’s history at the front

of the clause (Teo & Ren, 2019). For instance, in “example f”as well as a lifelong commitment to learning... It shows that they lifelong partner in education by keeping their faculty and alumni as well as professionals and leaders in industry, politics and society, at the forefront of the latest developments with on-going, research-based continuing education programs. Therefore, there are many thematization genre in the mission statement of TUM. Hence, the process of moving adverbial

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